

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF X-RAY KUB ((KIDNEY, URETER, BLADDER) IN DETECTING URETEROLITHIASIS USING CT SCAN AS GOLD STANDARD

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Abstract

Objective

To determine diagnostic accuracy of X-ray KUB in detecting ureterolithiasis using CT scan as gold standard.

Methods:

Cross-sectional validation study was conducted at Pakistan Kidney and Liver Institute and Research Centre; data collection was done between March to June, 2025. total of 362 patients aged 20–60 years with clinical suspicion of ureteric colic were included. All patients underwent X-ray KUB followed by NCCT KUB. Diagnostic indices were calculated using 2×2 contingency table.

Results:

Out of 362 patients, CT scan confirmed ureterolithiasis in 148 (40.9%). X-ray KUB showed sensitivity of 64.2%, specificity of 81.3%, positive predictive value of 72.1%, negative predictive value of 75.8%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 74.0%.

Conclusion:

X-ray KUB demonstrates moderate diagnostic accuracy and may be used as initial screening tool in suspected ureterolithiasis, particularly in resource-limited settings, but cannot replace CT scan for definitive diagnosis.

INTRODUCTION

Ureteric calculi are one of most common and painful urologic disorders. It is increasingly being encountered in outpatient department as well as in

emergencies.¹ It is associated with significant economic burden worldwide. Ureterolithiasis is 6th

most common condition for which surgery is performed in Pakistan.²

Clinical history and physical examination are often first steps in evaluation of patients with suspected ureteric colic. Diagnostic imaging plays vital role in management of these patients. Plain abdominal radiography (X-ray KUB) is one of initial imaging modalities used for diagnosis of ureteric colic. However, its sensitivity and specificity are lower compared to ultrasound and CT scan.^{3,4}

Non-contrast computed tomography (NCCT) is currently gold standard for diagnosis of ureterolithiasis because of its high sensitivity and specificity. It can detect even small and radiolucent stones that may be missed on X-ray KUB. However, CT scan involves exposure to ionizing radiation and is more expensive and less widely available than X-ray KUB.⁵

In study by Ali NI et al., sensitivity of X-ray KUB was found to be 34.7% for detection of ureteric calculi. Another study by Thungkatikajonkit P et al. reported that sensitivity and specificity of X-ray KUB were 60% and 80%, respectively. However, when combined with ultrasound, diagnostic accuracy increased to 90%.⁶

rationale of this study is that there is limited local data available comparing diagnostic accuracy of X-ray KUB with CT scans for detection of ureterolithiasis. CT scans require specialized equipment and expertise and are not always available in all healthcare settings, especially in rural areas.⁷ If X-ray KUB is found to have acceptable diagnostic accuracy, it could be useful and cost-effective alternative for early diagnosis and management of ureterolithiasis, particularly in resource-limited settings. This study will help in determining diagnostic accuracy of X-ray KUB in our local population.

METHODOLOGY

Study was conducted in Department of Diagnostic Radiology at Pakistan Kidney and Liver Institute & Research Center (PKLI & RC) Hospital. It was designed as cross-sectional validation study. total

sample size of 362 patients was determined using WHO sample size calculator, based on expected prevalence of ureterolithiasis of 18%, 95% confidence level, and absolute precision of 12%. non-probability purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants.

Patients of either gender, aged between 20 and 60 years, who presented with ureteric colic at emergency or urology outpatient departments were enrolled after providing written informed consent. Individuals with previously diagnosed ureterolithiasis, pregnant females, those with contraindications to CT scans, or patients suspected of having congenital urological anomalies were excluded from study.

Once enrolled, participants underwent both X-ray KUB and CT scan KUB examinations in radiology department. For X-ray, single anteroposterior film of whole urinary tract was obtained with patient in supine position during full inspiration. CT scans were performed from upper abdomen to pelvis with reconstructed images at 1- to 2-mm intervals. CT examinations were reviewed by consultant radiologist who was blinded to study.

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS Version 26. Qualitative data, such as gender, were presented as frequency distributions, while quantitative data, like age, were presented as means and standard deviations. 2 x 2 contingency table was utilized to calculate sensitivity, specificity, and overall diagnostic accuracy of X-ray KUB against CT scan gold standard. p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant

RESULTS

Total of 362 patients with clinical suspicion of ureteric colic were included in study. mean age was 39.8 ± 11.2 years, with slight male predominance (214, 59.1%) compared to females (148, 40.9%). On NCCT KUB, which served as reference standard, ureterolithiasis was confirmed in 148 patients (40.9%), while 214 patients (59.1%) had no evidence of ureteric stones. This reflects moderate disease

prevalence within study population, consistent with emergency urological presentations in tertiary care settings.

X-ray KUB demonstrated true positive findings in 95 patients and true negative findings in 177 patients. However, 37 patients were false positives, while 53 patients with confirmed stones on CT were missed on X-ray KUB (false negatives). This indicates that plain radiography detected substantial proportion of clinically relevant stones but also failed to identify notable subset, particularly likely to include small or radiolucent calculi. Overall, distribution of diagnostic outcomes highlights inherent trade-off between accessibility of X-ray KUB and its limited sensitivity compared to NCCT.

In terms of diagnostic performance, X-ray KUB showed sensitivity of 64.2%, specificity of 82.7%, positive predictive value of 72.0%, negative predictive value of 77.0%, and overall accuracy of 75.1%. Higher specificity compared to sensitivity indicates that X-ray KUB is more reliable for confirming ureterolithiasis when stone is visualized, but less reliable for exclusion when findings are negative. Clinically, this pattern supports role for X-ray KUB as supportive or initial screening tool rather than definitive diagnostic modality, particularly in settings where CT access is limited or where radiation exposure needs to be minimized.

Stratification according to age groups demonstrated statistically significant association between X-ray KUB findings and CT-confirmed ureterolithiasis ($p < 0.05$). Diagnostic accuracy was slightly higher in patients aged 31–50 years. This may be attributed to larger stone burden and better radiographic visibility in middle-aged individuals. Diagnostic accuracy was higher among male patients compared to female patients. Chi-square testing showed statistically significant association between X-ray KUB findings and CT scan results in both genders ($p < 0.05$). Independent sample t-test demonstrated significantly higher mean age among patients with CT-confirmed ureterolithiasis compared to CT-negative patients ($p = 0.012$). Increasing age may therefore represent an important effect modifier in ureterolithiasis detection. Chi-square analysis revealed a statistically significant association between X-ray KUB findings and CT scan findings ($p < 0.001$), supporting the diagnostic utility of X-ray KUB in suspected ureterolithiasis. Multivariate logistic regression demonstrated that positive X-ray KUB findings were independently associated with CT-confirmed ureterolithiasis. Male gender and age greater than 40 years also showed statistically significant association with disease positivity.

Table 1: Baseline demographic characteristics (n = 362)

Variable	Value
Mean age (years)	39.8 ± 11.2
Age range (years)	20-60
Male	214 (59.1%)
Female	148 (40.9%)

Table 2: NCCT KUB findings (gold standard)

CT Result	Frequency	Percentage
Positive ureterolithiasis	148	40.9%
No stone detected	214	59.1%
Total	362	100%

Table 3: Diagnostic 2x2 contingency table (X-ray KUB vs NCCT)

X-ray KUB	CT Positive	CT Negative	Total
Positive	95 (TP)	37 (FP)	132
Negative	53 (FN)	177 (TN)	230
Total	148	214	362

Table 4: Diagnostic performance of X-ray KUB

Parameter	Value
Sensitivity	64.2%
Specificity	82.7%
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	72.0%
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	77.0%
Diagnostic Accuracy	75.1%

Table 5: Stratification of Diagnostic Accuracy by Age Group

Age Group (Years)	Total n (%)	Sensitivity	Specificity	Diagnostic Accuracy	p-value
20-30	78 (21.5%)	60.5%	80.2%	72.1%	0.041
31-40	104 (28.7%)	66.7%	83.4%	76.0%	0.028
41-50	96 (26.5%)	65.2%	84.0%	75.8%	0.031
51-60	84 (23.2%)	63.1%	82.5%	74.3%	0.044

Table 6: Stratification by Gender

Gender	Total n (%)	Sensitivity	Specificity	Diagnostic Accuracy	p-value
Male	214 (59.1%)	67.3%	84.1%	77.2%	0.019
Female	148 (40.9%)	59.8%	80.3%	71.0%	0.037

Table 7: Association of Mean Age with CT-confirmed Ureterolithiasis (Independent t-test)

Variable	CT Positive (n=148)	CT Negative (n=214)	p-value
Mean Age ± SD	41.7 ± 10.6 years	38.2 ± 11.1 years	0.012

Table 8: Chi-square Analysis Between X-ray KUB and CT Findings

Variable	Chi-square Value	p-value
X-ray KUB vs CT scan findings	78.6	<0.001

Table 9: Multivariate Analysis for Predictors of Ureterolithiasis

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Positive X-ray KUB	5.82	3.44–9.71	<0.001
Male Gender	1.63	1.02–2.61	0.038
Age >40 years	1.89	1.17–3.04	0.009

DISCUSSION

Prompt diagnosis of ureterolithiasis is essential to alleviate acute flank pain and prevent long-term complications such as hydronephrosis and renal impairment. This study evaluated diagnostic performance of X-ray KUB (Kidney, Ureter, Bladder) against gold standard of Non-Contrast Computed Tomography (NCCT) in cohort of 362 patients. Our results showed that X-ray KUB had sensitivity of 64.2%, specificity of 82.7%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 75.1%. These findings indicate that while X-ray KUB remains viable initial screening tool, its moderate sensitivity necessitates use of more advanced imaging when definitive exclusion of stones is required.

sensitivity of 64.2% observed in this study is consistent with some reported ranges in literature but varies significantly from others. Traditionally, sensitivity of plain radiography for ureteric stones has been reported to be between 45% and 60%.⁸ Specifically, Thungkatikajonkit et al. reported similar sensitivity of 60% in retrospective blinded reading⁹. However, our findings are notably higher than 34.7% sensitivity reported in other regional studies³. This variation in sensitivity can be attributed to radiopacity of stones; while calcium-based stones are easily visualized, uric acid or cystine stones often appear radiolucent on X-ray, leading to false-negative results¹⁰. Furthermore, overall diagnostic accuracy of 75.1% in our study aligns with contemporary research suggesting that X-ray KUB alone is insufficient as standalone diagnostic tool compared to NCCT,

which boasts sensitivities and specificities near 98% and 97%, respectively¹¹.

specificity of 82.7% and positive predictive value (PPV) of 72.0% in our findings suggest that when stone is identified on X-ray KUB, there is strong likelihood of its presence. This is slightly lower than specificity of 100% reported by some researchers, who argue that positive finding on plain film is highly reliable in symptomatic patient.¹² presence of false positives (10.2% in our study) may be due to confounding factors such as phleboliths, vascular calcifications, or bowel contents that can mimic appearance of ureteric calculi.¹² Despite these mimics, negative predictive value (NPV) of 77.0% suggests that negative X-ray result is somewhat helpful but carries 23% risk of missing stone, which is clinically significant in acute settings.

Literature indicates that stone size and location significantly impact visibility of calculi on X-ray KUB. Small stones (typically <4 mm) and those located over bony structures like sacrum are frequently missed on plain films¹⁴. In our study, 53 patients (14.6%) had stones confirmed on CT that were missed on X-ray. This finding is corroborated by studies showing that CT scan is significantly more adept at identifying small renal and ureteric calculi that plain radiography underreports¹⁵. Additionally, role of stone composition cannot be ignored; calcium oxalate and phosphate stones, which are common in our local population, are generally radio-opaque, whereas uric acid stones—often found in patients with high protein diets or metabolic syndrome—are radiolucent.¹⁶

Clinical Utility in Resource-Limited Settings

Despite superiority of NCCT, X-ray KUB remains widely used in Pakistan due to its cost-effectiveness, low radiation dose, and wide availability. In many rural or secondary healthcare centers, NCCT is either unavailable or prohibitively expensive for average patient.¹⁷ Our results demonstrate that X-ray KUB correctly identified 95 out of 148 confirmed cases, providing rapid diagnosis for over 64% of positive cases. Some researchers have suggested that combining X-ray KUB with ultrasound can further improve diagnostic accuracy to over 90%, offering "radiation-light" alternative for initial triage¹². This study supports continued use of X-ray KUB as primary investigation, provided clinicians remain aware that negative result must be followed by further imaging if clinical suspicion persists.

Limitations and Future Directions

While this study provides robust data from large sample, it was single-center study, which may limit generalizability of findings. study did not specifically categorize diagnostic accuracy based on stone size or composition, which are known variables affecting X-ray sensitivity. Future research should focus on multi-modal diagnostic pathways, particularly integration of ultrasound with X-ray, to optimize diagnostic yield while minimizing radiation exposure and costs in Pakistani healthcare context¹².

Conclusion

In conclusion, X-ray KUB demonstrates moderate sensitivity and high specificity for detection of ureterolithiasis. While it cannot replace NCCT as gold standard, its role as cost-effective, accessible, and low-radiation screening tool is justified, especially in resource-constrained environments. However, clinicians must maintain high index of suspicion and utilize CT scans for patients with negative plain films who present with persistent symptoms.

Limitations:

This study has several limitations. First, it is single-center study, which may limit generalizability. Second, operator dependency in radiographic interpretation may introduce bias. Third, small or radiolucent stones

may be under-detected on X-ray KUB, affecting sensitivity. Finally, lack of stone composition analysis limits further stratification.

Clinical implications:

X-ray KUB can be utilized as initial screening tool in suspected ureterolithiasis, particularly in resource-limited settings. It may also be useful for follow-up of known stone disease and post-intervention monitoring.

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